

IMPROVING AND ANALYZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT PULSAR LLC

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Abstract. In this article, the analysis of marketing activities requires the study of the main economic indicators of the enterprise, since the results of marketing activities are reflected in financial and economic indicators. The financial performance of manufacturing enterprises is an indicator of how well they have achieved their strategic and current goals.

Key words: Product, production, enterprises, company, drinks, beer, volume, market, assortment.

УЛУЧШЕНИЕ И АНАЛИЗ МАРКЕТИНГОВЫХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЙ В ООО «ПУЛЬСАР»

Аннотация. В данной статье анализ маркетинговой деятельности требует изучения основных экономических показателей предприятия, так как результаты маркетинговой деятельности отражаются в финансово-экономических показателях. Финансовые результаты производственных предприятий являются показателем того, насколько хорошо они достигли своих стратегических и текущих целей.

Ключевые слова: Товар, производство, предприятия, компания, напитки, пиво, объем, рынок, ассортимент.

INTRODUCTION

The number of enterprises for the production of consumer goods in the Samarkand region is growing from year to year. The fact that entrepreneurs are empowered by independence is not only the breadth of their initiatives. There are also opportunities to attract foreign investors. This is one of the first enterprises in Samarkand with foreign capital. LLC "Pulsar".

Brewery and beverage company Pulsar in the form of LLC is located at st. Ozod Shark 2, Samarkand and began operations on May 22, 1993. In 2005, as a result of the merger of Pivzavod No. 1, Samarkand Praga and Samarkand-Prague-Pivo, LLC Pulsar Group Brewing Company was created. In order to capture the Uzbek market, the joint venture is aimed at further development. In 2012, the Uzbek-German joint venture Pulsar Group Brewery JV and Ziyobakhsh-Uni-Trading merged to form today's Pulsar Group Brewery joint venture. Business website <http://pulsar.uz/>.

Changes in the assortment of JV LLC Brewery Pulsar Group in 2019-2020 Table 1

t / y	type of product	Share in production, %	
		Dec 2019	Feb 2020
1	Beer Pulsar	58	61
2	Beer Asia	16	23
3	Pulsar Drinks	12	5
4	Mineral water Pulsar	6	2
5	Mineral water Samarkand	4	2
6	Juices	4	7

The company specializes in the production of beer, soft drinks and mineral water.

Analyzing the product line, it accounts for 84% of beer products, 14% of various drinks and 4% of mineral water (Table 1).

The assortment of goods for individual brands can be seen in the table below (Table 2).

Product range of JV LLC Brewery Pulsar Group in 2020

table 2

No.	Name of product	The size	
		Sony, min don	Amount, thousand Soums
1	Mineral water "Rulsag" 1.5l PET	858,00	128,700.00
2	Closed drink "Orange" 1.5l.	132,00	38,280.00
3	Cherry cold drink 1.5l.	78.00	22,620.00
4	Cold drink "Green Apple" 1.5l.	126.00	36,540.00
5	Cold drink "Cola" 1.5l.	126.00	36,540.00
6	Cold drink "Lemon" 1.5l.	90.00	26,100.00
7	Cold drink "Raspberry" 1.5l.	42.00	12 180.00
eight	Beer "Rulsar-Zolotoe" 0.33l. aluminum jar	45.00	13,500.00
nine	Beer "Rulsag-Light" 0.5l.	15.00	4,500.00
ten	Beer "Rulsag - Light" 1.5L PET.	40.00	11,600.00
eleven	Beer "Rulsag-Exclusive" 0.5l	45.00	19350.00
12	Beer "Rulsag - Exclusive" PET 1.5L	66.00	66,000.00
13	Beer "Rulsag-V1ask" 1.5L PET.	36.00	34560.00
fourteen	Beer "Rulsag-Gold" 0.5l.	555,00	205 350,00
15	BEER "Rulsag-Gold" 1.5L PET	510.00	397,800.00
16	BEER "Rulsag-Silweg" 0.5l	552,00	358,800.00
17	BEER "Rulsag-Silweg" 1.5L PET	540,00	178,200.00

The enterprise has created all the conditions for the production of high-quality and competitive products. Its main production facilities include: malt workshop, brewery, fermentation workshop, filtration workshop, special barrel filling workshop, bottling workshop, finished product warehouse, packaging and raw materials workshops.

As of 2020, the company employs 160 people, whose skills and experience are enough for the company to take a leading position in our country.

Pulsar Group Brewery LLC is the main dealer of the brewery. There are small businesses in other regions as well. And through them the goods are distributed to other regions. The range of products of JV LLC Pivovarnya Pulsar Group in the form of LLC: Pulsar-Silver, Pulsar-Black, Pulsar-Gold, Pulsar-Light and Pulsar-Exclusive,Asia ", Beer "Standard", "Standard Plzen". There are also soft drinks: Pulsar-Orange, Pulsar-raspberry, Pulsar-Lemon, Pulsar-Green apple, Pulsar-Cherry, Pulsar-Cola, as well as the mineral waters Pulsar and Samarkand.

Analyzing production indicators, we see that the volume of beer production has increased in recent years (table 2).

Changes in beer production at the Pulsar Group Brewery JV in 2016-2020 **Table 3**

Year	Production volume, thousand dal.	Chained method change dynamics		Dynamics of changes compared to 2016	
		Min gave.	%	Min Dal	%
2016 Nov.	2340.0	0	100	0	
2017 Nov.	2436.0	+94	104.1	+94	104.1
2018 Nov.	2550.0	+114	104.7	+210	108.9
Dec 2019	2772.3	+222.3	108,7	+432.3	118.5
Feb 2020	3024.0	+251.7	109.1	+684	129.2

As can be seen from the table, beer production at the Pulsar Group Brewery JV is growing steadily. This is clearly seen in the diagram below (Figure 2).

Figure 3. Change in beer production volumes at the Pulsar Group Brewery JV in 2016-2020, Dal.

RESEARCH METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

These data show that the production volume at the Pulsar Group Brewery JV has been growing steadily in recent years. Average production growth rates in 2016-2020 averaged 11.7%, an increase of 70% in 2020 compared to the results of 2016, which indicates the strengthening of the company's market position. The slight slowdown in growth in recent years is due to the emergence of many competitors on the beer market.

Beer is a seasonal product and its production also varies with the season. The bulk of production falls on the summer. The table below shows production figures by month (Table 4).

Implementation of the plan for the production of beer in the joint venture Pulsar Group Brewery in 2020

Table 4

months	Reja, dal	fact, gave	differences	
			gave	%
January	93,000	83,022.80	-9,977.20	89.3
February	153,000	113,215.90	-39 784.10	74.0
March	227,000	217,805.60	-9,194.40	95.9
April	400,000	350 462.50	-49,537.50	87.6
May	440,000	409,703.00	-30,297.00	93.1
June	435,000	414,869.30	-20 130.70	95.4
July	440,000	412,053.00	-27,947.00	93.65
August	425,000	401 101.40	-23,898.60	94.38
September	295,000	263 955.10	-31,044.90	89.48
October	179,000	160 152.70	-18,847.30	89.47
November	148,000	148,462.00	462.00	100.31
December	65,000	49 196.80	-15,803.20	75.69
During a year	3,300,000	3,024,000.00	-276,000.00	91.64

It can be seen that according to the forecast in 2020 it was planned to produce 3,300,000 dollars of beer, but in reality, 3,024,000 bottles of beer were produced, which is 91.64% of the plan. If we trace production by month, we can include the months April to August and, to a lesser extent, September as the main production months.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Analysis of marketing activities requires the study of the main economic indicators of the enterprise, since the results of marketing activities are reflected in financial and economic indicators. The financial performance of manufacturing enterprises is an indicator of how well they have achieved their strategic and current goals. Therefore, in order to determine the effectiveness of advertising activities, we studied the results of economic activities in 2020 based on the financial statements of JV "Pulsar Group Brewery" (Table 5). Table 5

In 2020 Main financial results of LLC JV LLC Pivovarnya Pulsar Group, thousand UZS.

No .	Indicators	2017 Nov.	Feb 2020	Growth rate, %
1.	Net sales from product sales,	4 868,506	7 993,060	164.1
2.	The cost of goods sold,	3 158,950	2 971,225	94.0
3.	Gross profit from product sales,	1 709,556	5 021 835	293.7
4.	Current expenses,	391 480	445,194	113.7
5.	From general business activities income,	1 253 390	4 502 307	359.2
6.	Until tax is paid Benefits,	1 253 390	4 502 307	359.2
7.	Income tax payable,	342 392	399 859	116.7
eight.	Net profit,	910,998	4 102,448	450.3

CONCLUSION

From the above data, we can conclude that the financial performance of the Pulsar Group Brewery JV in recent years has grown rapidly along with the growth of production. Sales revenue in 2020 increased by 1,509,874,000 soums and amounted to 146% compared to 2017. The cost of production increased by 1,173,329,000 soums and amounted to 145% compared to 2017. The relative cost reduction of the Pulsar Group Brewery JV resulted in an increase in gross profit and net income. At the same time, we can observe that the cost of production is still quite high, and the net profit is 78.8%.

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